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Classroom Innovation: Addressing English Classroom Needs Through Design Thinking

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Abstract: : The study, in response to the challenges faced by the Department of Education (DepEd), aimed at providing innovative solutions to problems in order to arrive at similar results obtained by researchers who have used Design Thinking. The study specifically utilized Design Thinking as an approach to address the English language classroom needs in the secondary level. The researcher utilized the qualitative research method as research design, specifically, the single case study design which aimed to expound on an existing problem using Focus Group Discussions. Six students and four teachers from public and private junior high schools provided data for the study. The results of the FGD showed that students identified specific problems that they encountered in an English language classroom at the secondary level. Such problems were identified as needs and became the starting point of teacher discussants in their Design Thinking orientation and workshop. In the process, Design Thinking provided promising innovative solutions in addressing problems in the classroom and may be used as a process in improving education.

Keywords: *Design Thinking, Classroom Innovation, English Language Teaching*

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Introduction

The study aimed at contributing innovative improvements in the learning environment in the junior high school, particularly in an English language classroom setting. This case study specifically utilized Design Thinking (DT) as an approach to address English classroom needs at the secondary level vis-à-vis open possibilities of using DT as an approach to address problems in the education sector.

The researcher studied the use of DT to provide innovative solutions to prevailing problems in education, particularly in the English language classroom. The present times demand change and innovation not only in the industry but in the field of education. Thus, it is fitting that an innovative approach such as DT be used in education. Positive results of applying DT in the field of education were presented in an array of studies, making it a promising and innovative approach in solving education-related problems (Brown 2008; Hattangadi, 2016; Kupstashtien & Lee, 2018; Schoenboom, 2013; Wrigley & Straker, 2015).

Purpose of the Study

The study applied the DT approach in improving the classroom experience of junior high school students.

Research Questions

1. What are the needs of students in an English language classroom?
2. How can Design Thinking be applied in the classroom?
3. What prototype can help address the identified needs of the students?

Theoretical Lens

In this case study, pragmatism provides a sufficient theoretical underpinning to establish how DT can provide a solution to identified English language classroom needs. According to Dalsgaard (2014), pragmatism can be operationalized to inform and guide concrete design projects and help understand and orchestrate the design process.

Pragmatism is considered a philosophical tradition, defined as the practical consequence following acceptance and belief. Woert (2016) explains pragmatism from the perspective of John Dewey, who asserted that things can only be understood by their connection to the contextual whole. This means that it is not possible to think or act on an abstract representation of something as it should be situated within a specific context.

Having said that, a situation that is identified to be problematic may be transformed into something temporarily stable, which is why the application of the design process is being conducted and applied in this study. Woert further explained that in pragmatism there is such a thing as inquiry. It is the mode of thinking and acting to transform an unstable situation. In this process, there is an attempt to identify an unstable situation; there is also an attempt to conceptualize what needs to be put into practice in the real world. If it fails, the process of continuously seeking for a possible solution continues.

Therefore, the DT process involves identifying a specific problem to be collaboratively solved and an attempt to produce innovative solutions. According to Lund (2014), the

desired result of DT is to change what is not currently working into something that meets the user's needs and improves their experience. Similarly, this study aims at providing possible solutions to identified problems by applying the DT process in the context of education.

Review of Related Literature

Defining Design Thinking

The use of the DT process as an approach to introduce innovation proves effective with the many claims and testimonies from different research fields. Studies proving its innovative effects are presented.

According to Pressman (2018), there is no general agreement on a precise definition of DT; there are variations across disciplinary cultures and different meanings depending on context. However, Brown (2008) provided a metaphorical definition of DT as a system of spaces rather than a predefined series of orderly steps. He particularly emphasized the three systems as inspiration, ideation, and implementation.

Cinar et al. (2017) explain that DT is not a tool applied to develop strategies and enhance innovation in business per se, but it is a prominent approach in all walks of life. Kolko (2015) further explained a set of principles collectively known as design thinking: empathy with users, a discipline of prototyping, and tolerance for failure. It is the best tool to create those kinds of interactions and develop a responsive, flexible organizational culture.

Lor (2017) defined DT as an innovative, creative, and human-centered process and mindset that employs collaborative multidisciplinary teams to generate user-focused products, services, and experiences. Ellis and Bernhardt (2017), in the other hand, defined it as an industry approach that helps designers think out of the box. Generally, Brown and Wyatt (2009) asserted that DT could lead to hundreds of ideas and real-world solutions to create better outcomes for organizations and the people they serve. Such promising definitions and discussion were evident in the following studies conducted in relation to the field of education.

Design Thinking in Education

According to Long (2012), DT in education can be regarded from the perspective of collaborative system thinking and a mix of creative and analytical habits, which may be able to assist students in improving the world. It was stressed once more that DT makes use of design to enhance the human experience. Collaboration, systems thinking, and the development of a healthy mix of creative and analytical habits were all incorporated in this essay. In a more profound sense, Schoeneboom (2013) noted that DT demands comprehension of the evolving nature of the modern industrial economy against the backdrop of the new Asia-Pacific century.

The implementation of DT would necessitate a paradigm shift in education, according to a study by Noel and Liub (2015), which provided a synthesis of current literature and preliminary analysis of DT in education as an intervention at the primary school level. Gallagher and Thordarson (2018) claim that educational leaders who also serve as designers believe that changing beliefs is always more difficult than changing behavior.

Additionally, it was stated that culture is a crucial element in the change process and that top-down change eliminates the voice and choice of adult learners.

Munyai (2016) investigated how DT may improve South Africa's education and training system. The researcher concluded that creative confidence is necessary in the education sector as it has to produce citizens who are ready to make a positive contribution to society and who are capable of coping with complex work environments. This is in consideration of the primary objective of DT, which is to solve problems.

Roth (2011) conducted research that aimed to develop a tool for assessment of the mindset and skills inherent in the design process, including building empathy, prototyping, developing a bias toward action, and fostering radical collaboration. Chin et al. (2019) believed that educators aim to equip students with learning strategies that they can apply when approaching new problems. They believed that teaching DT strategies may support this goal.

Similarly, Hattangadi (2016) explained that DT is a formal method for the practical and creative solution of problems, with the intent of improving future results.

Kwek's (2011) study looked at how DT, a novel model of learning, may be applied to instruction. It may be possible to gain a deeper knowledge of what will inspire and propel teachers to use this novel technique through lesson observations and interviews. His research revealed that teachers had "appropriated" this new instructional instrument in numerous, distinctive ways to suit various goals, learning environments, and subjects rather than being passive recipients of the instrument. Another important conclusion is that how DT was employed to connect with classroom learning is still driven by mastery of academic core content. Thus, emphasis was placed on the requirement to develop academic content understanding and 21st-century skills as equally crucial student outcomes.

According to Evan (2016), DT raised student engagement. By using DT, there is a chance to create a learning environment that promotes student agency and increases engagement. She added that redesigning a learning space is about changing not only the physical environment but also the way that learning takes place. Furthermore, Riddle (2016) noted that DT acts as a framework that aids in problem definition, empathy for others, development of potential solutions, and the refinement of those answers via numerous iterations until a workable answer has been produced. DT improves students' learning by providing students with a proven method for applying their knowledge and abilities in relevant ways while also considering how the same practice may benefit the school.

According to Schoeneboom (2013), DT is increasingly acting as a catalyst for innovation. Scheer et al. (2012) endorsed this innovation when they stated that DT fosters multidisciplinary projects and approaches difficult phenomena in a holistic, constructivist manner, thereby meeting the essential criteria of effective 21st-century learning.

Design Thinking and English Language Teaching

Nunan (2009) suggests that rethinking the nature of language, learners, and the learning process can also lead to new methods of conducting Second Language Teaching and Learning (SLTL). This may be a result of efforts to come up with fresh approaches to problems, difficulties, or conundrums encountered when teaching, which leads to the

conclusion that methods ought to be tested in studies first.

According to Roy and Brine (2013), incorporating DT into regular language instruction in EFL contexts is a novel pedagogical strategy. Using case study analysis with Japanese students majoring in computer science, the results of the study suggested that design-based language learning strategy might encourage grammatical comprehension through writing practice, methodical reasoning, schematization, presentation, and structured content authoring. Results further suggest that using design rubrics with examples, frequent feedback, and practice in online design analysis could pave the way for more methodical and higher-order thinking among students.

Newman (2018) highlighted the fact that the DT framework fostered generative analysis that produced insights into the process of design, which shapes personal pedagogy and classroom practices that improve instruction and which illustrates the value of engaging in the process rather than the production of a product. This agrees with the findings of Tu et al., (2018), who claimed that DT may improve teaching and promote student participation. Wrigley and Straker (2015) also provided an approach with a holistic classification of DT educational content. This is the first step in developing a multidisciplinary DT curriculum.

Fredrickson (2017) toyed with the question of how DT can be used to create an ESL program for newcomers. Overall, the implication of applying DT to ESL programming proved to be challenging but rewarding when it came to the gradual process of developing sustainable programming opportunities for underrepresented students. The researcher identified challenges for newcomers in this context but also pointed out that the benefits of the program outweigh these challenges as they create an impact in the overall school culture.

Evans (2016) shared that DT increased student engagement. Creating a learning space through DT is about fostering student agency at the outset where students become more engaged. She further added that more than the interior design project, rethinking a learning space is about remaking not only the space but also the learning that occurs.

The researcher shows tremendous promise in filling in the gap in the literature about the status of the English language teaching and learning in the Philippines by employing DT as an innovative way to improve learning environments (Maliksi, 2010; Martin, 2014). The studies implementing DT in education offer a lot to guarantee that the students of today will be able to fulfill the demands of tomorrow. With numerous claims and testimonies from various fields that are supported by research, the adoption of the DT process as a method to introduce innovation demonstrates its effectiveness. In the examination of related literature, research demonstrating its innovative benefits is included.

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher utilized the qualitative research method as research design. Wallen and Fraenkel (2013) explained that this method considers the setting of interest to observe and collect data. Particularly, Thomas (2017) claims that the case study approach entails in-depth study of a single case or a smaller group of related cases. Examining certain case elements in-depth is intended to produce a rich, comprehensive understanding of a particular topic. A case study shows a real-world issue that could arise in the course of

regular business operations.

This case study aimed to contribute to the initial initiatives of the DepEd to improve the learning environment in Philippine schools. Primarily, in this case study, the goal of the researcher is to address the needs of an English language classroom in Cavite and to introduce an innovative method in providing solutions to existing problems using Design Thinking.

Research Locale

The researcher conducted the study in Cavite. Aside from residing in the said province, it was assumed that schools and the student population will increase drastically in the future since Cavite is rapidly developing and industrializing. The schools were selected because of their accessibility to the researcher. However, due to the pandemic, safety measures and restrictions were observed. The researcher reverted to selecting participants coming from the private and public schools to participate in the study. The participants were chosen using the convenience sampling method.

Participants from the private schools were selected because these schools adhere to the minimum standards stipulated in the K to 12 Minimum Learning Competencies set by the DepEd. However, it also provides leeway for private schools whose curricula and philosophy, mission, and vision are aligned with the DepEd's specific goals. Participants from the public schools were selected because these schools strictly implement and adhere to the prescribed curriculum and memorandums from the DepEd. Participants from these schools provide a rich and concrete experience of the prescribed curriculum because they adhere to the DepEd.

The onset of the pandemic greatly affected the process of this research. Instead of conducting the study on a specific, physical venue, the researcher utilized Facebook Messenger instead. This virtual environment allowed the researcher to safely connect with the participants without the threat of contracting any disease. This type of environment also limited the participants' personal contact with each other. However, this ensured that all participants were safe from the threat of the prevailing pandemic.

Data Sources

According to Brancati (2018), an FGD is ideally composed of 6-12 participants. The population of the study consists of six Grade 10 junior high school students, four public and private junior high school English teachers, and two English language experts teaching in the higher levels. The participants of the study were selected using the convenience sampling method. The researcher was not able to reach the ideal number of participants and specifically used this sampling method due to the prevailing pandemic that restricts face-to-face interactions.

The researcher analyzed documents that contributed to a deeper understanding of the context of the study. Specifically, the researcher selected documents issued by the government related to the implementation of the K to 12 program, which is the present curriculum; the K to 12 Tool Kit and the prescribed Junior High School Curriculum Guide for English prescribe the minimum standards for instruction and assessment. An informal class observation was conducted for the researcher to identify classroom and teaching practices

at the junior high school level.

Grade 10 students were selected because they have gone through the whole junior high school level and could provide a rich experience of the curriculum. The researcher particularly used FGD to document the experiences of the participants. The documented and transcribed data were then interpreted using a thematic approach. This allowed common themes to be clustered and interpreted.

The first FGD was conducted to determine the participants' experiences. Six Grade 10 students from the private and public schools participated in the first session. This enabled the researcher to extract their experiences and views about their English language classrooms.

The second FGD was conducted with the four teacher discussants that came from both public and private schools. They teach English at the junior high school. Before the FGD session, the discussants were first gathered for the DT orientation through Facebook Messenger video call. This was to allow the discussants to experience DT first-hand and to be able to determine how DT can be used as an approach to answering the needs of the students. The researcher recognized the possibility that the data might change if the participants increased in number.

Due to the strict protocols and the abrupt changes caused by the pandemic, two former junior high school English language teachers presently teaching at the higher levels were selected and were given a blank template to play the role of the last process in the DT approach. The researcher was not able to reach the Test part of the DT process because of the prevailing situation.

Research Instrument

The researcher used a Personal Data Sheet to obtain the basic information of the respondents, particularly their name, age, gender, grade level (for the students), and years of experience (for the teachers). This represented the diversity of the participants taking part in the study.

An FGD Guide is a set of questions that extract the experience of the discussants. The researcher utilized three sets of FGD: the guided FGD for the students and the guided FGD for the teachers and the experts. The researcher used this to structure and organize the flow of discussion. Data extracted from this research tool were thematically interpreted to identify prevailing themes that would answer the specific statement of the problems. The instruments were validated by three experts in English Language Teaching to ensure the appropriateness of the instruments in answering the research questions.

Audio recordings were used to ensure that the researcher captured the experience of the discussants in the study. The research first asked for the consent of the discussants to ensure that the participants were comfortable and their identity was protected. This is similar to the FGD notes that were taken to counter-check the transcripts taken from the FGD to ensure that the interpreted information is accurate and exact. Furthermore, the researcher assured the participants that the data would be destroyed once the case study is done.

Data Collection Procedure

The recruitment of the discussants utilized convenience sampling; the students were randomly selected, while the teachers were selected based on their specialization, experience, and profession. The experts were selected based on their expertise in the field of education.

The discussants signed a consent form to participate in the FGD. The first copy was given to the participants and the second copy was kept by the researcher. Participants were informed of the audio recording for data collection purposes. Demographic data were collected from the discussants using questionnaires collected after the FGD session.

The FGD data for student discussants were utilized to identify the needs of the students based on their perspective. Sixty minutes were allotted for every session with the student discussants, while the teacher discussants were given a half-day session for their orientation, workshop, and FGD session. The two English language teachers were given a blank template for their feedback that served as the Test part of the DT approach. The teachers were first given an orientation on the DT process for them to understand and appreciate how DT can be used to address the needs of the students in an English language classroom. The orientation was done virtually through Facebook Messenger. This is due to the strict implementation of the COVID 19 safety guidelines. After this, the researcher facilitated the FGD for the teachers.

The researcher used a discussion guide in facilitating the FGD by highlighting the topics that needed to be covered. This also allowed the participants to raise their issues and concerns about how they address the pressing needs in their respective institutions. During the FGD, the researcher encouraged the discussants to have an in-depth exploration of the topic, reflect on their practices, and raise any issues they encountered.

A DT workshop was conducted before the FGD session with the teachers. Each teacher participant was asked what they thought of the workshop and how it could help them improve the learning environment. The flow and results of the workshop were stated in the FGD Report.

The FGD sessions were audio-recorded as agreed with the participants and were transcribed verbatim for analysis. The recordings were secured until transcribed and then destroyed. The transcription did not contain information that would allow individuals to be linked to specific statements. Confidentiality was strictly observed.

Data Analysis Procedure

Collected data were analyzed using thematic analysis. Maguire and Delahunt (2017) explained thematic analysis as a process. The first step of the framework was reading and re-reading of the transcripts. The second was to generate codes. The third step was to search for themes. The fourth was to review the themes. During the fifth step, the researcher defined the themes. Lastly, the sixth step was where the researcher provided a report of the thematic analysis.

The case study particularly exhausted related public and personal documents that established how DT pedagogy can be used to address identified needs.

The researcher particularly followed O'Leary's (2014) eight-step process which begins with the gathering of relevant texts and development of an organization and management scheme. The researcher then produces a duplicate of the documents for annotation and secures the original manuscript. The researcher then assesses the authenticity of the documents before ruling out biases before proceeding with the exploration of the documents' context and background. Afterward, questions are created to extract the necessary information from the content.

Specific methods are utilized because pertinent documents are manageable and practical, making them an efficient and effective way of gathering data. These may be composed of firsthand information that may be substantial in establishing the grounds for argument.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher sent the participants a letter of invitation stating the extent of their participation in the study and the possible benefits that they will be able to get in the study.

The students were given a separate consent form for their parents to sign since they were still underage. The researcher ensured the participants that no personal data will appear in the study and that all tools used in the study will be destroyed after the case study is completed. All participants of the study agreed and signed the consent form.

Result

This part of the study discusses the themes extracted from the three FGDs. The presentation of these themes will follow the analysis of how these themes can contribute to the extant literature.

According to Blyth et al. (2011), central to the DT methodology is connecting personal stories with a need for action and such a strategy is in no way limited to Design Thinking. Long (2012) elaborated this by emphasizing that by learning to observe human behaviors and needs in real-life, DT participants discover human-centered questions and problems worth trying to solve. In short, DT is about using design to improve the human experience.

Research Question 1. What are the needs of students in an English language classroom?

The students' answers were clustered according to themes. The researcher was able to come up with the following:

Need for Positive Learning Environment

Students lack confidence in expressing and participating in classroom activities because the classroom environment does not make them feel confident and appreciated. Therefore, the students' learnings were hindered.

The learning environment is a haven for the students' learnings. It positively accepts and corrects mistakes and allows learning. According to Waldman (2016), for students to learn, they must feel safe, engaged, connected, and supported.

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Need for Varied Teaching Strategies and Technology-integrated Instruction

Students find it difficult to learn because of the teacher's repetitive teaching strategy. Using a learner-centered approach, the teachers consider the students' interest as a top priority in designing instruction. This is followed by the teachers' assessments to ensure that, aside from engaging activities, content and required competencies are addressed and related to real-life situations. Motteram (2013) explained that technology is very much a part of language learning throughout the world, at all levels. Similarly, it encourages students to participate because it is a familiar avenue to them. In addition, it expands their creativity because of the array of tools that they can use to express themselves.

The Use of Appropriate Assessment

Nunan (2009) explained that assessments are the tools, techniques, and procedures for collecting and interpreting information about what learners can and cannot do. Assessment plays a critical role in the teaching and learning process and it is the same for ELT. It provides an avenue to quantify the students' grades, basis for feedback, and validation of learning. It is paramount that appropriate and varied assessments are given to students.

The need for real-life application of the target language

According to Duff (as cited in Murcia et al. (2014)), Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) is an approach to language teaching that emphasizes learning a language to communicate with others. This allows students to be able to use communication as a tool to connect and survive in the real world. As an approach, it introduces students' to real-life situations where they can use the language that they learned.

The teachers identified specific student needs from the themes that were derived from the students' answers in the FGD. This is because of one of the features of the K to 12 curriculum, which states that "it is relevant and responsive as it centers on the Filipino learner; it is developmentally appropriate and focuses on succeeding in the 21st century. Moreover, the curriculum responds to the needs of the community" (K to 12 Toolkit, 2012, p. 4).

Research Question 2 How can DT be applied in the classroom? The researcher clustered the themes extracted from the FGD sessions and produced from the teachers' responses.

Values Experience

"It considered the views of the students which is a rich input."

The process provided necessary evidence that DT values human experience. True to its nature of being human-centered, these experiences can evolve into a possible innovative solution. The process encapsulated not only the experience of the students, considered to

be the end-user of the classroom environment that teachers designed, but also the experiences of the designers in the process, the teacher-discussants. These two sets of experiences became combined allowed the development of ways to address identified English language classroom needs.

In a study conducted by Husain and Khan (2016), over two-thirds of both students and professors believed that faculty development can benefit from student feedback. Similarly, when this feedback becomes the school's basis in improving the learning environment and experience of the students, it may clear the way for problems that may have not been seen in the past years. Steen (n.d.) cited Gallian Parrish in an article, stating that "student voices, not only inform the moment but, are powerful assessment tools for future learning as we work to fill in gaps in understanding and tailor class activities for our students."

Fosters Collaboration

"The student and teacher can easily collaborate because they could share their ideas and whereabouts regarding the English language."

Collaboration is a key component in the 21st century and in Design Thinking. Through this, innovative solutions may be conceived because of different minds thinking and exchanging thoughts about a specific challenge or problem. This is very much encouraged in all aspects of education, most especially in class participation. Laal (2012) believed that collaboration helps solve critical issues in society. Goertz (2015) explained that collaborative spaces allow critical thinking for new materials to be created and problems to be solved. Imagine students' outcomes and outputs when they collaborate. Imagine teachers when they are collaborating. Now, imagine students and teachers collaborating, discussing pros and cons, improvements, etc. DT fosters these characteristics. It enables designers to tap various points of view and generate an array of possible solutions to challenges and problems.

Hobcroft (2017) explained that DT evolved at many organizations as a way to solve problems in creative and innovative ways. It is an approach that develops problem-solving skills that employ empathy, ideation, prototyping, and experimentation to help solve real-world issues. It is human-centered, putting a premium on humans and human needs.

Various studies in the field of education that had applied DT in their respective fields have consequently provided innovative results (Scheer et al., 2012; Schoeneboom, 2013; Ordonez et al., 2017; Ellem 2018). Design Thinking, at the primary level, was also proven to improve the learning experience of students (Noel & Liub, 2015). Aflatoony and Wakkary (2015) established a connection between DT and the 21st century. Studies on the application of DT, as a teaching strategy, have also given promising results (Fredrickson, 2017; Wrigley & Straker, 2015). An array of DT applications was also done in higher education which gave significant contributions to the proposition that DT has the same effect in various fields (Withell & Haigh, 2013; Munyai, 2016). Specific studies were also conducted in the field of Business Education (Mootee, 2013; Cinar et al., 2017; Matthews & Wrigley, 2017).

Problem Solvers through Creative and Critical Thinking

"Means of proposing prototypes that can be used in the future to address the students' difficulties in the subject."

DT triggers creative and critical thinking as designers develop prototypes that could address the needs of a specific challenge or problem. Constantinides (2015) explained that being creative helps teachers solve problems. She elaborated that this is not new to teachers. It is something that they do every day as they decide on teaching materials, procedures, grades, etc. Johnson (2015) agreed that creative teachers are not gifted in creation per se, but they are masters at gleaning ideas from all kinds of sources. Significantly, being creative is vital for teachers. Similarly, Williams (2016) identified critical thinking as an important skill in the 21st century. The DT approach leads teachers to the proposition that teachers in the DT approach are creative and critical thinkers because of their significant contributions in identifying problems, developing prototypes, and presenting innovative solutions to address identified needs.

Rizzo et. al (2017) used DT for the public sector innovation and social innovation from a two-fold perspective: as an emergent trajectory of innovation in the public sector and as a framework on which to design the process of change in public organizations. The paper introduced a design-based learning framework to support employees to develop new competencies by taking part in a service design project. Clark and Smith (2008) argued that DT can help any profession solve problems in innovative ways. Dorst (n.d.) identified it as a new paradigm for dealing with problems in different industries like Information Technology and Business.

Provides Innovative Solutions

“It involves innovation as well.”

The innovative characteristic of DT was evident from the beginning to the end of the process. The value of the students' perception cannot be set aside in the process. Instead, it was the driving force for the teachers to innovate. In the process, the students' feedback was not used to improve the teachers. Instead, they were used to improve the learning environment, specifically the English language classroom. It was not done to ridicule the teachers or to simply give praise to the teachers. Instead, the teachers used the students' inputs to improve the learning experience of the students in the classroom by devising an additional component to their usual rubric.

Findıkoğlu and İlhan (2016) mentioned that innovation is of vital importance in transforming and reconstructing learning environments along with the curricula, the role of the teacher, and teacher training.

Schoeneboom (2013) discussed the role of design to improve the quality of human life and in challenging economic times. Liedtka et al. (2013) shared the same sentiments when they deliberated that DT may look more pedestrian than miraculous, but it is capable of reliably producing new and better ways of creatively solving a host of organizational problems.

Thus, themes 3 and 4 responded to the claim that the K to 12 Curriculum focuses on the acquisition of 21st-Century Skills as part of the learning goals.

Initiates Educational Transformation

“Do not limit Design Thinking in just one subject but rather make it an approach applicable to all.”

DT is not limited to addressing English language classroom needs. It may be used in all

aspects of education like curriculum, instruction, assessment, and management. If students or teachers continue to find challenges and problems that they believe should be improved in their respective fields and should be provided innovative solutions, DT will best fit their endeavor. DT has proven itself effective from its origin and may provide educational transformation through innovative solutions.

Generally, according to Lund (2014), the desired result of DT is to change what is not currently working into something that meets the user's needs and improves their experience.

Thus, the themes extracted from the teachers' FGD are a clear manifestation of their response to the proposition of the former DepEd Secretary Bro. Armin Luistro, FSC, when he stated in a message that, "the impetus for meaningful education reform is clear: the realities of our modern world require a different kind of Filipino. The Filipino must be a lifelong learner. The Filipino must be holistically developed. The Filipino must be globally oriented and locally-grounded..." (K to 12 Toolkit, 2012, p.1).

However, their prototype did not reach the evaluation level due the limitations in physical mobility of the student participants' who were considered the end users. Two English language teachers in the higher levels commented on the prototype and the DT process presented below constitutes the answer to the third research question.

The participants used improvisation as a teaching strategy to establish a positive learning environment. Through this strategy, students will be able to maximize their potential and talent in their anticipated class participation. The participants discussed how they utilized "improvisation" in their own classrooms and how it might be able to address the identified needs of the students in their respective classrooms.

Research Question 3 What prototype can help address the identified needs of the students?

The English language teachers in the higher levels were the participants who were asked to comment on what prototype/s they have in mind. Participants were given ample time to present their suggestions and ideas. After careful discussion of possible prototypes for the identified problem, the consolidated decision of the participants was to include Improvisation in the rubrics used for students' task.

English language practitioners #1

The DT process can help educators revisit their instruction process. In the field of education, traditional teaching is valued, hence, its discussion is the primary focus while the teacher is the only source of knowledge. But in DT, students and teachers are gleaned as builders of knowledge. The key concept *ideate* believes that a positive classroom set up is necessary for learning. Gone are the days when teachers would plan everything, from lessons, strategies, to assessments. Instead, they work hand in hand with students to ensure that learning takes place without sacrificing the students' interests.

I believe that it all starts with the national agency, the DepEd. It should be the one to promote this approach because public and private institutions follow its orders. The DepEd should adapt the DT approach to highlight critical thinking, empathy, and analysis among students. Seminars, wide information dissemination, and workshops must be provided to teachers; effective materials and assessments to highlight Design Thinking should also be

constructed. The idea is to produce students with lifelong skills who can think and innovate solutions to their country's problems. Do not limit DT to just one subject but rather make it an approach applicable to all. In this way, one can see that skills are not the primary indicators of a learned man/woman, but the ability to solve problems outside the classroom.

English language practitioners #2

The K to 12 is ambitious yet ideal. It is overwhelming since it deals with a myriad of interconnections. Each component in the framework is essential to the learning and teaching process yet seem congested that schools fail to emphasize or implement it fully.

DT is a way to create better classrooms and learning environments for students. It also taps on the 21st-century skills or abilities that students need to develop to succeed in this information age. The processes involved in DT promote critical thinking, creative thinking, collaboration, and communication among students. Furthermore, DT will lead to educational transformation. Since the primary issues presented in the FGD include a positive learning environment, teaching strategies, appropriate assessment, and the use of technology, DT aims to improve English language instruction.

The first stage of DT (Empathize) allows English language teachers to evaluate the needs of their students. In the Empathize process, teachers set aside their assumptions and gain real insight into users and their needs. By knowing the learners and their needs, teachers can begin ideating the teaching strategies that best work for the individual and group needs of their learners. They may consider the use of technology to pique the interest of their learners and engage them in creative learning activities. Assessment may also be at the end of the DT process where teachers can execute and evaluate their instruction.

This study sought to determine the use of DT in addressing English language classroom needs in junior high school. It is a qualitative, single case study that utilized Focus Group Discussion in gathering data from Grade 10 junior high school students and junior high school English language teachers, both from the public and private schools in Cavite. Data were analyzed using content analysis. The themes, as a result of the study, presented a promising solution to address the problems in the English language classroom in the junior high school in possessing 21st-century skills expected from both the teachers and the students.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the researcher, therefore, recommends the following:

1. Future researchers should explore other variables or important components of education.

DT exhibits the potential to provide innovative solutions. The researcher suggests using DT in improving curriculum, instruction, assessment, leadership, classroom management, systems, and policies.

2. English teachers should use the DT approach as a means of providing innovative solutions to problems.

DT may be exercised in addressing identified needs, systems, and policy development; it

may also be used as a teaching strategy and as a way to develop students to become 21st-century learners. Educational administrators should use DT to improve practices.

Implications

Theory and Knowledge Building

The study provides the academic community an innovative solution by using qualitative data as a driving force to initiate the improvement of the learning experience of students, particularly in an English language classroom. While current practices such as standardized tests determine how the latter can be improved, this study advocates the use of concrete experiences using the DT approach as a process that seeks to provide innovative solutions.

Professional Practice

The study brings to light the value of experience to determine outcomes that meet the demands of the 21st century. Specifically, it addresses how the school prepares students for the future. Thus, the results of the study negate the idea that standardized tests can determine how learning innovation improves learning. The study proposes the use of experience as a basis of improving the learning process and experience of students through an innovative solution that processes these experiences as a vital component in the process of seeking improvement.

Program and Policy

Teachers, school managers, and academic leaders are recommended to revisit their practices on how they improve processes and policies. With this, academicians should explore Design Thinking not only in the classroom but as a mindset. DT offers a promising solution to current and future problems because of its process of going back to the end users' experience and cultivating changes that introduce innovation.

Creativity and Innovation

The study offers creativity and innovation through DT as an approach to providing solutions to potential problems. DT itself is creative and innovative because of its unique process fostered by empathy, defining, ideation, prototypes, and test. This approach is unique since empathy is an element in the process.

Socio-cultural Implications

The study utilized DT as an approach that offered an opportunity to improve systems that involve several stakeholders. This proves to be beneficial to all stakeholders who are involved in the process because DT is a human-centered approach.

Ethico-moral Implications

Problems cannot be solved when a solution is readily offered; however, when people are involved in the problem and they try to look for a solution together, there could be promising results. When students have poor performance, teachers readily provide judgment based on scores and not based on the learners' experience. The problem arises when the learner is not allowed to reflect on the process. But if learners and teachers are allowed to improve processes and systems based on their experience, this changes everything since both have

a reflective experience that teaches them that sustainability comes when people collaboratively identify a solution.

Summary

This study sought to determine the use of DT in addressing English language classroom needs in junior high school. It is a qualitative, single case study that utilized Focus Group Discussion in gathering data from Grade 10 junior high school students and junior high school English language teachers, both from the public and private schools in Cavite. Data were analyzed using content analysis. The themes, as a result of the study, presented a promising solution to address the problems in the English language classroom in the junior high school in possessing 21st-century skills expected from both the teachers and the students.

Conclusion

In general, the preceding items present the results of using DT as a solution to the identified needs of the students. This leads to improving the English language learning environment. Furthermore, the themes developed in this study are not only limited to the improvement of the English language classroom; it also responds to the call of the DepEd to contribute innovative solutions in improving the student's learning environment.

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